

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Post-return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Afghanistan

WP8 Country Survey Report

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About the GAPs

GAPs is a Horizon Europe Project that focuses on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers to international cooperation on returns. The project aims to address the disparities between the anticipated outcomes of return policies and their actual results by challenging the dominant, one-sided understanding of "return policymaking." Specifically, GAPs:

- Identifies the missing link in the EU's return policy, considering both its internal and external dimensions.
- Explores factors that facilitate or hinder international cooperation.
- Illuminates the returnees' experiences and sheds light on the factors that shape their resilience, aspirations and hope in the face of adversities.

The GAPs project is structured into 11 Work Packages, each designed to critically examine the existing legal, policy, and institutional frameworks governing return and reintegration processes. These Work Packages aim to identify best practices, uncover structural and operational gaps, and strengthen the overall effectiveness of return governance and management by generating evidence on returnees' lived experiences, resilience, and hope in the face of mounting adversities. Using a field survey-based approach, the project generated evidence-based insights to inform more coherent, equitable, and sustainable return policies.

GAPs fieldwork has been conducted in 14 countries: Jordan, Lebanon, Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Türkiye, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq. This country report has been compiled in the context of the GAPs Work Package Eight (WP8) on 'Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Afghanistan.

Post-Return Practices and Experiences of Returnees in Afghanistan

The WP8 focuses on the experiences of returnees in four countries: Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, and Tunis – this report focuses on Afghanistan. By conducting representative surveys across these contexts, the objective is to gain a deeper understanding of returnees' aspirations, motivations, and challenges during and after their return. To achieve this, the study employed standardised measurement tools, including the Hope Scale, Resilience Scale, and Depression Scale. These tools allow us to assess the psychological well-being of returnees and examine how broader societal (e.g., community support, social inclusion) and structural factors (e.g., access to services, legal documentation, employment opportunities) influence their ability to cope with adversity. Ultimately, the aim is to identify patterns of vulnerability and strength among returnees and to provide evidence that can inform policies and interventions aimed at supporting sustainable reintegration.

Map.1: Afghanistan¹

¹ University of Texas at Austin, University of Texas Libraries (2009), access date, Mach 06, 2025, https://maps.lib.utexas.edu/maps/middle_east_and_asia/afghanistan_admin-2009.jpg

1. Country Context: Afghanistan

The Afghan government has framed return as a national priority and placed the High Commission on Returnees within the Ministry of Refugees and Repatriation (MoRR), under cabinet-level oversight. Despite its centrality, there is little public documentation on the Commission's routine functioning. Data for this analysis were collected through the triangulation of policy and administrative documents on the High Commission, unstructured discussions with senior officials (November 2025), and field observations at registration and reception sites in Kabul and Mazar-e-Sharif.

The Commission's governance structure operates on two levels: a Strategic Level and an Operational Level. The Strategic Level, reflecting a dual-track approach, comprises twelve committees: six focused on emergency relief (shelter, food, health, and legal support) and six on long-term reintegration (education, infrastructure, land allocation and the development of returnee settlements, and social integration). The Operational Level implements these directives through functional subcommittees at border hubs and reception sites.

Operations are concentrated at Torkham, Spin Boldak, Islam Qala, and Nimroz, with linked reception camps such as Anzargi and Omari. Implementation is coordinated with UNHCR, for registration support, emergency shelter, and cash and in-kind assistance (UNHCR 2025c) and with IOM, which focuses on safe transit, immediate relief, and support to vulnerable groups (IOM 2025). Other UN agencies, international NGOs (INGOs), and local NGOs provide counselling and socio-economic support, particularly for women and other vulnerable groups.

The operational workflow comprises the following steps:

Border intake & verification: At "zero points," teams register individuals/families, verify identities, and record education and vulnerability profiles; each case receives a unique reference number - coordinated and supported by UNHCR and IOM, including other UN agencies such as the United Nations Development Program for Afghanistan, Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC).

Immediate relief & protection: Health checks, vaccinations, and nutrition screening are conducted; food and safe water are distributed, along with SIM cards for telecommunication

Transport & relocation: Free onward transportation is provided to reception camps (e.g., Anzargi) or to destination provinces.

Temporary accommodation & camp services: Shelter is allocated and WASH/Non-Food-Items (NFI) provided; partner agencies deliver sectoral services under Commission coordination, with co-located government/INGO.

Education: Provincial Directorates administer standardised proficiency assessments for school-age returnees lacking documents; a certificate of level is issued, and students are placed accordingly

Financial assistance: Eligibility is verified, and cash assistance is disbursed in coordination with partners to avoid duplication; amounts are benchmarked to short-term rent and food

needs where applicable - coordinated and supported by national and international non-state partners and UN agencies

Resettlement & land allocation: After verification/inspection, plots are distributed using the formula one *Biswa* (~100 m²) per household member, with coordination to meet minimum service standards (water, sanitation, road access, proximity to schools/clinics).

2. Methodological Framework

The purpose of this report is to provide a detailed account of the administration, analysis, and findings of the desk review and survey of Afghan returnees conducted by the Bilim Organization for Research & Social Studies (hereafter BILIM) in coordination with Uppsala University (Faculty of Theology). The literature review includes an in-depth analysis of policy papers, legal documents, regional and bilateral agreements, as well as government and non-governmental reports on return governance and reintegration.

Before starting the field survey, BILIM formalised collaboration with the MoRR by signing a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the MoRR. Before beginning the field survey, BILIM formalised its cooperation with the MoRR by signing a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU). This MoU specifically outlined the overall objectives of the GAPs project, particularly WP8, and detailed the proposed implementation plan for the GAPs initiative.

In preparation for the field survey, BILIM obtained a random sample of 210,000 returnees from MoRR for 2013 onward. This dataset was comprehensively disaggregated by province, return destination, and country of return. Parallel to this initiative, BILIM obtained a certificate of clearance from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the Ministry of Public Health of the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan. The process of securing this clearance to conduct the field survey involved submitting a fully completed application form, including the questionnaire, for review and approval.

Given the complex political landscape in Afghanistan and the increasing politicisation of NGO activities, we proactively engaged with MoRR's provincial offices, including local police departments, to facilitate the smooth implementation of the survey. This coordination posed challenges at the provincial level, including Kandahar, where the de facto authorities had imposed restrictions on the operations of many international NGOs. Despite these constraints, BILIM successfully surveyed the selected provinces.

2.2 Digital Integration of Data Collection Tools

The instrument development team initially configured the SurveyCTO application by inputting the survey questions into the system. This process involved deconstructing complex questions, defining the logic and conditions for question flow, and setting up appropriate answer options. As a result, some questions were divided into multiple components within the application to ensure clarity and accurate data capture. The questionnaire comprised 213 questions. However, not all questions were posed to every respondent. Depending on the specifics of each case, some questions were asked while others were skipped. For example, if a respondent mentioned receiving financial assistance as part of a voluntary return program, they would also be asked how much they received (whereas returnees who had not received

aid would not be presented with this follow-up question). Following the interviews, the quality control team used the application's built-in quality assurance features to conduct a thorough review. This included verifying the accuracy and completeness of the data and ensuring compliance with established data quality standards.

2.3 Sampling

From the randomly generated list of 210,000 returnees since 2013 provided by the MoRR, a total of 416 Afghan returnees were randomly selected and surveyed across four provinces: Kabul, Herat, Mazar-e Sharif, and Kandahar. A two-stage stratified approach was adopted; in stage one, returnee settlements were randomly selected in each province and in stage two, returnees were randomly chosen from those settlements for interviews. The survey was conducted in person, with the assistance of SurveyCTO (Dobility, 2019), by seven trained interviewers from the organisation between December 27, 2023, and January 17, 2024. The sample was evenly distributed across the four provinces. A sample size of 416 is statistically reasonable for many types of survey analysis, particularly for estimating proportions with a 95% confidence level and a margin of error of approximately $\pm 5\%$, assuming a reasonably homogeneous population. Notably, all respondents had returned to Afghanistan within the past 10 years—i.e., since December 2013 for those surveyed in December 2023.

2.3 Structure of the Data Analysis

The following sections provide a summary of the basic demographics of the participating refugees, descriptive statistics for the survey responses, and a review of the lines of enquiry undertaken on the data for academic research.

3. Demographics

Of the total 416 Afghan survey respondents, most ($n = 332$) were male, while a smaller proportion ($n = 84$) was female. The mean age of the respondents was 33.1 years ($SD = 10.5$). In terms of marital status, 301 were married, 64 were single, 28 were engaged, and 23 were widows/widowers (for details see Table 1). Regarding the province where respondents resided at the time, 108 were from Kandahar, 106 from Herat, 102 from Balkh, and 100 from Kabul (see Map 2). In terms of ethnicity, 209 were Pashtun, 114 were Tajik, 42 were Hazara, 29 were Uzbek, eight were Arab, and four were Turkman ($n = 10$ defined themselves as “other”).

Table 1

Age, Gender and Marital Status

Characteristic	Category / Statistic	n	% / Value
Age (years)	Mean (SD)	416	33.1 (10.5)
Gender	Male	332	79.8
	Female	84	20.2
Marital status	Married	301	72.4
	Single	64	15.4
	Engaged	28	6.7
	Widow/widower	23	5.5

Map 2

Geographic Distribution of Respondents in Afghanistan

Regarding education, 156 reported being illiterate, while 92 stated they had completed upper secondary education (level 3). A total of 63 and 55 indicated that they had completed primary education (level 1) and lower secondary education (level 2), respectively. A lower number, 22, reported having completed post-secondary (non-tertiary education—level 4). While none had reported completing any short-term tertiary education (level 5), 16 reported having completed a bachelor's or equivalent degree (level 6). Finally, a total of 10 survey participants reported having completed some form of early general childhood, and two respondents specified "Other" as their form of education.

The average household size (i.e., number of total members living under the same roof) was 7.0 ($SD = 3.1$). Additionally, among respondents who reported being married or widowed ($n = 324$), 150 reported having male dependents aged 6-18, while 143 reported having female dependents. In terms of stated employment, most ($n = 203$) reported being unemployed. Besides those reporting being unemployed, stated professions included service and sales workers ($n = 41$), professionals, e.g., chemists, civil engineers, and pharmacists, and teachers ($n = 35$), elementary occupations, i.e., cleaners or labourers ($n = 21$), technicians and associate professionals, e.g., draftspersons, manufacturing supervisors, chefs ($n = 15$), skilled agricultural, forestry, and fishery workers ($n = 14$), craft-related trade workers ($n = 11$), armed forces occupations ($n = 7$), clerical support workers ($n = 7$), plant and machine operators and assemblers ($n = 7$), and only three managers. In terms of business links in the region, only two people reported having such connections.

In terms of general socio-economic status, 126 respondents reported monthly incomes of less than 5000 Afghanis (70 USD), with many (118) reporting no income at all. Incomes between 5000 and 10,000 Afghanis were reported by 114 respondents, while 39 participants reported an income between 11,000 and 15,000 Afghanis. Higher monthly incomes were rarer as follows: 16,000 to 20,000 ($n = 9$), 21,000 to 25,000 ($n = 6$), 26,000 to 30,000 ($n = 1$), 31,000 to 35,000 ($n = 1$), 36,000 to 40,000 ($n = 1$), 46,000 to 50,000 (i.e., 647.50 USD to 703.80 USD; $n = 1$). Therefore, with the latest net national income per capita estimated at 341 USD (24,000 Afghanis) per month (World Bank Group, 2025a), only a few respondents reported earning more than the country's average. Compared to the incomes they earned before leaving for their home country, most ($n = 294$) stated that they are now earning less, while 92 stated that they are now earning about the same. However, 30 returnees stated that they were now earning more. Furthermore, of the 416 returnees surveyed, 165 (39.7%) reported being employed or engaged in income-generating activities upon return. Of the 416 respondents, 59 stated that they had started a business venture upon returning. However, in terms of level of satisfaction with the performance and profitability of the stated venture, 22 (37.3%) stated that they were very satisfied, and 19 (32.2%) stated that they were satisfied, with others neutral ($n = 14$), dissatisfied ($n = 3$), and very dissatisfied ($n = 1$). In terms of being able to meet their basic financial needs, only 22 stated "yes, totally", and 44 stated "somewhat". A larger proportion of returnees stated "a little" ($n = 99$), "not really" ($n = 186$), and "not at all" ($n = 65$). Finally, in terms of securing loans or accessing credit for business or personal purposes since returning to Afghanistan, only 52 returnees stated "yes".

In addition, most returnees ($n = 226$) stated that they rented their homes; 98 indicated that they owned their homes; 59 said they were involved in a *Khaima* (tent) arrangement; 30 stated they leased their premises; and 3 indicated they had a bank loan.

To sum, with over 20% female representation, balanced sub-samples from the four regions, diverse ethnic and socio-economic groups, the current sample provides for quite reasonable

representation of the larger target group of returnees. Attention will now be given to the more substantive results about the lived experience, sentiments, and aspirations of the surveyed returnees.

4. Countries that Returnees had Originally Aspired to Travel to

In response to the question, “Which country was the destination for which you emigrated from Afghanistan?”, returnees provided a variety of reactions. While most initially aspired to emigrate to Pakistan ($n = 208$), many also planned to relocate to Iran ($n = 98$). Smaller proportions had aspired initially to emigrate to Türkiye ($n = 41$), Germany ($n = 32$), France ($n = 14$), Sweden ($n = 10$), and the United Kingdom ($n = 3$). Even fewer had aspired to emigrate to Western countries, including the USA, Canada, Australia, Belgium, Greece, and Italy ($n = 10$, with fewer than 2 per country). Figure 1 provides a visual for these results.

Figure 1

Initial Destination Countries that Returnees Had Aspired to Emigrate to

5. Date and Route-of-Return Country

Most respondents reported returning to Afghanistan in 2023 ($n = 223$) and 2022 ($n = 91$), with a small number reporting returning in 2024 ($n = 11$). The number of respondents that specified their return earlier was as follows: 2021 ($n = 17$), 2020 ($n = 35$), 2020 ($n = 35$), 2019 ($n = 18$), 2018 ($n = 6$), 2017 ($n = 9$), and 2016 and earlier ($n = 6$). Notably, the number of refugee returnees sampled per year mirrors official statistics from the UNHCR (2025b), with numbers minimal during the immediate post-Taliban takeover period, then increasing substantively in 2022 and 2023 (Official number of total refugee returnees: 2020 pop. = 2,147, 2021 pop. = 1,429, 2022 pop. = 6,506, and 2023 pop. = 54,870).

In terms of the countries through which *returnees had returned*, Pakistan ($n = 211$) and Iran ($n = 144$) featured prominently. Türkiye also featured, with 45 respondents reporting that this country was the last they had been in before arriving in Afghanistan. Finally, Germany and Sweden also featured three and four respondents, respectively.

Figure 2

Route-of-Return Country for Returnees to Afghanistan

6. Asian Countries Travelled to as an Emigrant

6.1 Primary Asian Countries Resided

Of the 416 respondents, 413 reported *spending time in an Asian country*. In terms of the primary *Asian* countries that respondents had spent most time in prior returning to Afghanistan, many reported residing in Iran (51.4%, $n = 214$) and Pakistan (47.1%, $n = 196$) with very few living mainly in ($n = 2$) and Malaysia ($n = 1$) (note that three persons withheld this information). Of the total 416 respondents, 106 also reported spending time in a second country—in these instances, Türkiye ($n = 67$) and Pakistan ($n = 31$) featured predominantly, with Saudi Arabia ($n = 2$), and India, Iraq, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan all featuring once as a secondary country. A minor proportion of 17 respondents also reported a tertiary country—for these respondents, Türkiye ($n = 12$), Iraq ($n = 2$), and India ($n = 1$) featured. Notably, one person had resided in four countries, including Iran, Pakistan, Türkiye, and India.

Notably, while the most common route-of-return country was Pakistan (Fig. 2), most returnees report having spent some time residing in Iran, while living in Iran for a period may provide comparatively more economic opportunities to Afghan refugees², reports of abuse and

² According to World Bank (2025b), in 2023, the Iran GDP per capita was 17,659.9 USD while the Pakistan GDP per capita was 6,036.7 USD.

deplorable detention conditions may make traversing the Iran-Afghan border riskier (Khan 2022).

6.2 Total Number of Trips to Asian Countries

The bar chart in Figure 2 provides a breakdown of the total number of trips³ that the returnees had taken to Asian countries as emigrants. Note that some returnees reported travelling up to four different Asian countries. In this instance, totals pertain to all primary, secondary, tertiary, and fourth-tier countries, where relevant.

Figure 2

Frequency Count for Total Number of Trips Returnees had Taken to Asian Countries

The most common number of total trips to an Asian country for an individual returnee was 1 ($n = 238$), and the second most frequent was 2 ($n = 105$). One respondent reported taking 17 trips (back and forth between several countries), however. Overall, although the most common number of trips was 1, the mean number of trips per returnee was 1.73 ($SD = 1.33$).

6.3 History of Asian Travel by Returnees

As stated, all returnees had travelled abroad in the ten years before the interview. However, a broad look at the history of emigration among the 413 respondents reveals that emigration began as early as 1965. Notably, the mean year of emigration among the 413 returnees was 2014 ($SD = 10.9$ years). Figure 3 illustrates all historical instances of immigratory travel by the returnees.

³ Multiple trips to the same country counted as a multiple. For example, a returnee reporting having travelled to Pakistan twice

Figure 3***Historic Instances of Asian Emigratory Travel for Returnees******6.4 Time Spent in Asian Countries***

Figure 4 presents the total number of years that returnees reported spending in every single Asian country.

Figure 4***Years Spent in a Single Asian Country for All Returnees***

While the most common period abroad was up to and including one year, the mean number of years was 7.8 ($SD = 11.9$), reflecting a long right tail with many extreme cases of sojourn. To note, one person reported being abroad for a total of 58 years before returning to Afghanistan.

7. European Countries Travelled to as an Emigrant

7.1 Primary European Countries Resided

A smaller proportion of returnees, specifically 26 individuals, reported having travelled to European countries during their time abroad. These 26 returnees reported spending time in up to eight different countries. For these 26 individuals, the total number of trips to the 16 European countries listed in Table 1 is provided.

Table 2

Total Number of Trips that 26 Returnees had taken to European Countries

Country	Total Trips
Greece	24
Serbia	11
Bulgaria	7
Croatia	7
Germany	7
Hungary	7
Austria	6
Sweden	4
Czech Republic	3
Italy	3
North Macedonia	3
Belgium	2
Denmark	2
Switzerland	2
France	1
Romania	1

Note. Multiple trips to the same country only counted as single trip.

7.2 Total Number of Trips to European Countries

Most of the 26 returnees who had ventured to Europe had made only one trip ($n = 9$). Figure 5 illustrates the total number of trips taken by the 26 individuals. Notably, the average (mean) number of trips was 3.4 ($SD = 2.4$).

Figure 5***Frequency Count for Total Number of Trips Returnees had Taken to European Countries******7.3 History of European Travel by Returnees***

A broad look at the history of emigration among the 26 respondents reveals that emigration began as early as 2014. Notably, the mean year of emigration among the 413 returnees was 2017 ($SD = 2.7$ years). Figure 6 illustrates all historical instances of immigratory travel by the returnees.

Figure 6***Historic Instances of European Emigratory Travel for Returnees***

7.4 Time Spent in European Countries

The bar chart in Figure 7 shows the total number of years that returnees reported spending in each European country. As illustrated, in most instances, returnees had spent only a very brief time in the European region, with an average of 8.5 months ($SD = 18.4$).

Figure 7

Years Spent in a Single European Country for All Returnees

Note. Each column represents a fifth of a year, i.e., 2.4 months.

8. Non-Asian and Non-European Countries Travelled to as an Emigrant

While no returnees reported travelling to any American or African countries, one stated that they had spent time in Australia. This involved a single trip in 2012, for which the respondents spent 5.5 years.

9. Likelihood of Legal and Illegal Re-Immigration

Respondents were asked about the likelihood for which they would legally and illegally re-immigrate to another country. With response options ranging from 1 = very unlikely to 5 = very likely. Notably, the mean response was low as 1.79/5.00 for the likelihood of legal re-migration and 1.58 for the possibility of illegal re-migration.

While most respondents stated that both legal and illegally forms of re-migration were not likely for them, substantial numbers of returnees stated that both legal and illegal forms of re-migration were possible. Figure 8 illustrates the proportions of responses in each category for the 416 returnees.

Figure 8**Reported Likelihood of Legal and Illegal Re-Migration of Returnees**

Note. Legal (very unlikely = 71%, somewhat unlikely = 5%, neither likely nor unlikely = 1%, somewhat likely = 18%, very likely = 5%; illegal (very unlikely = 76%, somewhat unlikely = 7%, neither likely nor unlikely = 1%, somewhat likely = 14%, very likely = 1%).

10. Motivations for Returning to Afghanistan

Returnees were asked to rate the relevance of 15 statements regarding their motivations for returning to Afghanistan. Table 2 provides details as to the significance of each statement.

Table 3
Motivations for Returning to Afghanistan

Reason	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Could not get visa/permanent residency in host country	28	49	10	90	239	4.11	1.29
Deported/forcibly removed from host country	37	59	8	57	255	4.04	1.42
I love my country (Patriotism)	99	76	16	130	95	3.11	1.53
People are being treated well in Afghanistan	140	112	19	121	24	2.46	1.36
Security situation in Afghanistan improved	170	119	4	72	51	2.31	1.46
People of the host country were unwelcoming or discriminating toward you	141	154	16	88	17	2.25	1.24
Poor security conditions in the host country	174	120	7	84	31	2.23	1.37
Poor economic conditions in the host country	163	133	11	80	29	2.23	1.33
Family reunification in Afghanistan	176	115	15	83	27	2.21	1.34
Unemployment in host country	154	156	11	67	28	2.18	1.27
Arbitrary Detention in transit and destination country	214	117	10	58	17	1.91	1.21
Economic conditions in Afghanistan improved	202	141	18	48	7	1.84	1.06
Because education has returned to Afghanistan	240	104	7	63	2	1.76	1.09
Refugees are being forcibly taken to war in the host country	243	142	29	2	0	1.50	0.65
Because of natural disasters in the host country	267	134	7	6	2	1.42	0.65

Note. *M* = mean response for item; *SD* = standard deviation of the response for the item; note that responses ordered by level of agreement with most relevant reason at the top and least relevant reason at the bottom.

As detailed, the most relevant reason for return was that the returnee “Could not get a visa/permanent residency in the host country” ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 1.29$) and that the returnee had been “Deported/forcibly removed from the host country” ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 1.42$). Notably, there was minimal variance in responses to the two least relevant motivators for return, namely “Refugees are being forcibly taken to war in the host country” and “Because of natural disasters in the host country”, suggesting that these motivators were not at all relevant.

To note, the primary motivator (or precursor) for return was the inability of returnees to attain residency or to be forcibly deported from the host country. This finding mirrors earlier research that surveyed over 10,000 Afghan people (The Asia Foundation 2017) that found that the motivations for return centred on struggles to access legal status in the host country or deportation.

11. Financial Support for Return to Afghanistan

11.1 Source of Financial Support for Return

All 416 reported leaning on some form of financial support to enable their return. In total, the 416 returnees received 618 instances of support from different sources. Figure 9 provides a breakdown of the 618 total financial support instances by type. The most common form of support was loans from friends and family (220 cases); thereafter, “savings” (194) ranked second. Support from IOM (83), UNHCR (48), gift from family/friends (37), sale of property (15), loan (2), and other.

Figure 9

Reported Likelihood of Legal and Illegal Re-Migration of Returnees

Note. Other = the Belgian government, the Swedish government, the Embassy of Afghanistan, the Swiss government, the Italian government, and Türkiye.

11.2 Support from Organisations

Of the 416 respondents, 131 reported receiving no form of assistance from any organisation as part of a voluntary return program. However, the remaining 285 reported a total 464 total instances of support from the following organizations: International Organization for Migration, IOM (242 cases of support), Afghanistan (50 cases), UN High Commissioner for Refugees, UNHCR (21 cases), European countries (8 cases), other national and international entities (6 cases), Türkiye (2 cases), and Iran (1 case).

In terms of financial assistance, Table 3 provides a breakdown of the organisations, their total expenditure, the number of returnees, and the average support provided to each returnee.

Table 4
Organizational Financial Assistance as Part of Assisted Voluntary Return Program

Organization	Total Expenditure (AFN)	Number of Returnees (n)	Average Expenditure (AFN)	Average Expenditure PP (USD ^a)
IOM	2,765,030	242	11,426	161
Afghanistan	311,000	51	6,098	86
UNHCR	729,000	21	34,714	489
EU countries	807,000	8	100,875	1,422
Türkiye	25,000	2	12,500	176
Iran	6,000	1	6,000	85

Note. PP = per person; conversion; ^aaccording to currency exchange (www.xe.com) as of 9 April 2025: 1AFN = 0.0141USD.

Notably, the IOM supported the most returnees, a total of 242 persons, and provided an average of 161USD to each of those returnees. Afghanistan also offered assistance, UNHCR, EU countries, Türkiye, and Iran, though to a lesser extent. Other smaller donations were also received from the UN (one instance: 141 USD), NRC (two cases: 141 USD and 352.5 USD), and the KRO (one case: 141 USD).

12. Detention Experiences Abroad

A substantial proportion of returnees had been detained while abroad. Of the total 416 respondents, 198 had reported spending time in detention. A total of 205 reported not being in detention, and 13 refused to answer that question. Therefore, close to 50% of all returnees had spent some time in detention while being overseas.

Regarding the total time spent in detention while abroad, most returnees reported spending less than two weeks (n = 80). However, others reported longer periods, including from two weeks to a month (n = 24), more than one month but less than two months (n = 21), more than two months but less than six months (n = 25), and more than six months (n = 9) (39 refused

to answer). Finally, 176 of the 198 returnees who reported being detained stated that the detention itself ultimately led to their deportation and return to Afghanistan.

13. Meaning in Life

Returnees were asked about the degree to which they derived meaning from the following four aspects of life: family, friends, religion, and work/school. Response options for each question were on a zero to 100% scale (with increments of 10), with 0 meaning no meaning at all and 100% meaning “to the fullest extent”. Table 4 summarises the results for each aspect of life.

Table 5
Where Returnees Find Meaning in Life

Factor	Percent (SD)
Family	93.9 (15.6)
Religion and Spirituality	93.1 (17.3)
Work/School	60.1 (38.9)
Friends	47.5 (35.3)

Note. *SD* = standard deviation of the percentage score.

Notably, family and religion contributed prominently to returnees’ sense of meaning in their lives.

14. Coping with Life’s Difficulties and Friendships

Returnees were asked how much each aspect of their lives helped them cope with life’s difficulties. Table 5 provides a breakdown of the relevance of each of the four prespecified facets.

Table 6
Where Returnees Find Support to Cope with Life’s Difficulties

Factor	Percent (SD)
Religion and Spirituality	89.8 (21.8)
Family	75.5 (36.0)
Work/School	56.5 (37.9)
Friends	44.9 (33.5)

Note. *SD* = standard deviation of the percentage score.

Notably, Religion and Spirituality feature strongly in this regard, with family, work/school, and friends also serving as ways to cope with life’s difficulties, though less strongly.

Regarding friendships, the average number of close friends reported by returnees was 1.91 (*SD* = 5.28). The minimum reported number of friends was zero ($n = 135$) while the maximum was 100. In the case of hardship or any other matter requiring immediate attention, returnees report that in most cases ($n = 385$), family would be the first point of contact, followed by friends ($n = 18$) and relatives ($n = 7$) (note that six persons reported having no potential support person).

15. Social and Cultural Connections

Of the total 416 returnees, 137 reported not attending a single social or cultural event. However, the remaining 279 participated at a total 530 events with the following frequency: Funeral (133 instances), Marriage (132 cases), Social gathering (mehmani, 126 instances), Khatem, Jomagi or Chel Ceremony (65 cases), form of social recreation (54 cases), birthday party (16 instances), and national procession (4 cases).

16. Application of Socio-Cultural Skills Learnt Overseas

In response to the question, “How often do you apply the socio-cultural skills learned in the host country in your daily professional interactions in your home country?”, most respondents ($n = 321$) reported “rarely or never”. The remaining responses for the alternative options indicated that such skills were applied only occasionally: slightly ($n = 41$), moderately ($n = 11$), significantly ($n = 22$), and extremely ($n = 21$). Similarly, the extent to which the socio-cultural skills that the returnees learnt abroad improved their ability to adapt to different cultural contexts in their own countries was also limited with responses as follows: not at all ($n = 285$), slightly ($n = 56$), moderately ($n = 22$), significantly ($n = 32$), extremely ($n = 21$).

Regarding the application of skills acquired abroad that were relevant to the jobs active returnees were engaged in, most reported that the skills were not at all relevant ($n = 313$) or only slightly relevant ($n = 20$). However, some thought that the skills learnt abroad were a little relevant ($n = 34$), somewhat relevant ($n = 21$), and very relevant ($n = 28$).

17. Hope, Resilience, and Depression among Returnees

Returnees reported varying levels of hope, resilience, and depression⁴. Figure 10 illustrates the level of hope exhibited by the returnees. Note that the instrument used to measure refugees’ hope (Snyder et al., 1991) included 12 items associated with higher levels of optimism for life and pursuit of goals alongside minimal levels of worry about one’s outlook (Appendix 1).

Figure 10 - Levels of Hope Exhibited by Returnees

⁴ See the 12-item hope scale ($\alpha = .83$), 10-item resilience scale ($\alpha = .90$), and 9-item depression scale ($\alpha = .70$) are available in the Appendix; note that all items exhibited positive point-biserial correlations—see item-rest statistic, CTT R package (Willse, 2018).

Hope levels reported by returnees ranged from 1.08 to 4.5 (response options ranged from strongly disagree = 1 to strongly agree = 5). The overall mean level of hope was 3.30/5.00 ($SD = 0.57$).

We used the 10-item Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (2003). Figure 11 presents a visual of the distribution of responses regarding returnees' resilience. The scale gauged returnees' mental capacity to manage misfortune, deal with pressure, and overcome challenges. Response options for each resilience item ranged between "not true at all" = 1 and "true nearly all of the time" = 5. In terms of resilience, returnees reported a mean of 3.57/5.00 ($SD = 0.74$). This overall score, equivalent to 71%, is comparable to that of Middle Eastern refugees residing in Australia who attained a median score of 67% on the comparable 25-item instrument (Ziaian et al., 2012).

Figure 11

Levels of Resilience Exhibited by Returnees

To estimate depression among returnees, we used the 10-item scale by Björgvinsson et al. (2013). The scale captured returnees' lack of focus, feelings of restlessness and inertia, and fear (see Appendix 1 for details). Following conventions in research practice, response options ranged from "never or rarely" (0) to "always or all the time" (3). The lowest reported mean was 0.22/3.00 across the questions, while the highest was 2.78/3.00. The mean response across items for returnees was 1.22/3.00, while a cutoff score of 1.00/3.00 or greater is commonly used to classify individuals as having "depressive symptoms". Therefore, of the total 416 returnees sampled, 275 (66.1%) could be classified as exhibiting symptoms of depression. Figure 12 provides a visual representation of the reported level of depression among returnees.

Figure 12

Levels of Depression Exhibited by Returnees

18. Conclusion and Recommendation

This report sheds light on the complex realities faced by Afghan returnees, drawing on data from 416 individuals surveyed in Kabul, Herat, Mazar-e Sharif, and Kandahar. The findings reveal a multi-layered and often precarious return and reintegration experience characterised by socio-economic vulnerability, limited access to basic services, and high levels of psychological distress. While returnees exhibited moderate levels of hope and resilience, nearly half reported detention abroad, and most returned due to forced deportation or an inability to secure legal residency in host countries. Reintegration remains challenging, with most returnees remaining unemployed and struggling financially. Although family and religious values provide significant psychosocial support, limited institutional assistance and socio-economic integration mechanisms further deepen returnees' vulnerability.

The structural and policy frameworks guiding return governance in Afghanistan—initially developed under the Republic and continued under the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan (IEA)—remain poorly implemented. Although MoRR and its affiliated directorates are tasked with coordinating reintegration efforts, their capacity is constrained by recent large-scale returns, particularly from Pakistan and Iran. Moreover, although a High Commission and subcommittees were established under the IEA to manage the latest wave of returns, their effectiveness remains unclear and under-documented.

The report also reveals gaps in the provision of adequate, sustainable economic opportunities for both returnees and local communities. While organisations such as IOM and UNHCR have provided support to returnees, this financial assistance is typically offered as emergency relief rather than as part of a strategy to promote sustainable economic livelihoods. In the absence of durable socioeconomic support mechanisms, most returnees are compelled to navigate extremely difficult living conditions with limited institutional support. As socioeconomic hardship persists, those in protracted return situations are repeatedly forced to adapt, often drawing on minimal resources. For many with broken hopes, resilience is no longer about recovery or progress. Still, it has come to reflect a set of survival strategies rooted in both personal endurance and communal solidarity. However, under these conditions, returnees

find meaning and coping primarily in family and religion/spirituality, as well as in school/work and friends.

The evidence from this report underscores the pressing need for targeted, coordinated, and rights-based interventions that are both responsive to returnees' immediate needs and supportive of long-term reintegration. Based on the findings from the ground, this report recommends the following key steps to support a more effective and sustainable return and reintegration process in Afghanistan.

Recommendations

- Enhance the operational and administrative capacity of the MoRR both at the national and provincial levels.
- Scale up tailored reintegration packages, including vocational training, business support, and prioritise locally driven employment creation initiatives, especially for youth and women.
- Ensure returnees have access to essential services, including healthcare, education, and housing. In this context, strengthen coordination between humanitarian actors and government bodies.
- Promote community-led programs to enhance social cohesion between returnees and host communities. Facilitate local dialogue and reintegration committees involving civil society and local authorities. Particularly, engage religious institutions, madrasas, and community leaders to facilitate dialogue, communication, and social networks.
- Establish trustful communication channels with state and non-state stakeholders, and hold regular meetings to facilitate and develop sustainable, long-term programs and projects that ensure durable returns and reintegration.
- Depoliticise return and adhere to tripartite agreements as the primary mechanism governing returns from both Iran and Pakistan
- Provide catch-up registration in the provinces for returnees who missed registration at zero points
- Ensure transport is available to all households, irrespective of size
- Establish time-bound procedures to prevent repeated delays in shelter and land allocation, caused by administrative bottlenecks
- Enforce transparent procedures for all aid distribution, particularly land and shelter allocation.
- Integrate psychosocial services into reintegration support. In this context, promote initiatives by local actors (family members, kin, friends, religious institutions, and community leaders) and international actors (INGOs, UN agencies) to strengthen healthy coping mechanisms and resilience practices.
- Promote bilateral and regional frameworks and establish the Return and Reintegration Research and Policy Centre that brings together members from state and non-state stakeholders in both host countries and the country of origin, including UN agencies. The centre would serve as a platform for actors with direct and indirect roles in developing and implementing policies to make return and reintegration sustainable between Afghanistan and Türkiye, Pakistan, Iran, and the broader EU region.
- Ensure that resettlement sites provide basic services and livelihood support with access to local economic opportunities

- Make sure reintegration processes and WASH/NFI support are designed and delivered to meet returnees' needs across seasons.

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Appendix 1

Section I: Hope						
[HopeQ1] Select the most appropriate response for each question						
No.	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
HopeQ1a	I can think of many ways to get out of a jam.					
HopeQ1b	I energetically pursue my goals.					
HopeQ1c	I feel tired most of the time.					
HopeQ1d	There are lots of ways around any problem.					
HopeQ1e	I am easily downed in an argument.					
HopeQ1f	I can think of many ways to get the things in life that are important to me.					
HopeQ1g	I worry about my health.					
HopeQ1h	Even when others get discouraged, I know I can find a way to solve the problem.					
HopeQ1i	My past experiences have prepared me well for my future.					
HopeQ1j	I've been pretty successful in life.					
HopeQ1k	I usually find myself worrying about something.					

HopeQ1	I meet the goals that I set for myself.					
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Section II: Resilience						
[ResilQ1] Please respond to each item.						
No	Statement	Not True at all	Rarely True	Sometimes True	Often True	True nearly all the time
[MigQ10nh1]	I am able to adapt when changes occur.					
[MigQ10h2]	I can deal with whatever comes my way.					
[MigQ10nh3]	I try to see the humorous side of things when I am faced with problems.					
[MigQ10nh4]	Having to cope with stress can make me stronger.					
[MigQ10nh5]	I tend to bounce back after illness, injury or other hardships.					
[MigQ10nh6]	I believe I can achieve my goals, even if there are obstacles.					
[MigQ10nh7]	Under pressure, I stay focused and think clearly.					
[MigQ10nh8]	I am not easily discouraged by failure.					
[MigQ10nh9]	I think of myself as a strong person when dealing with life's challenges and difficulties.					

[MigQ10nh10]	I am able to handle unpleasant or painful feelings like sadness, fear, and anger.					
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Depression Scale					
No.	Statements	Rarely or none of the time (less than 1 day)	Some or a little of the time (1-2 days)	Occasionally or a moderate amount of time (3-4 days)	All of the time (5-7 days)
DepressionQ1a	I was bothered by things that usually don't bother me.				
*DepressionQb	*I had trouble keeping my mind on what I was doing				
DepressionQ2c	I felt depressed				
DepressionQ2d	I feel that everything I do is an effort to remain alive.				
DepressionQ2e	I am optimistic and hopeful about the future [R].				
DepressionQ2f	I felt fearful.				
DepressionQ2g	My sleep was restless				
DepressionQ2h	I was happy [R]				
DepressionQ2i	I felt lonely.				
DepressionQ2j	I could not "get going"				
<i>Note.</i> *Item not included as loaded negatively; R = reversed.					

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